

Underlying Social Dynamics of Solar Home Systems Installation in Remote off-grid Communities in Lagos, Nigeria

by

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Abstract

Remote off-grid communities are often situated far from centralized power infrastructures and, as a result, do not have access to grid electricity. Solar home system, an inexpensive renewable technology for self-generating electricity, is now available to households in Lagos State including those in remote communities. However, adapting global solar home system deployment strategy within remote communities in the state is hindered by limited knowledge of the local social dynamics involved in the spread of the technology. Utilizing interpretative phenomenological analysis, this research paper offers insights into endemic social influence processes that facilitate adoption and expansion of solar home systems in three neighbouring remote off-grid communities on Tomaro Onisiwo Island in Lagos State. Interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) is a qualitative research approach used to explore individuals' subjective experiences of a particular phenomenon. The approach provides a nuanced understanding of interpersonal interactions that influence the adoption of solar home systems in this research. The findings from the research suggest that persuasion, word of mouth, and observation of users of the technology are influencing adoption of solar home systems in the three neighbouring remote off-grid communities on Tomaro Onisiwo Island in Lagos State.

Keywords: *solar home system, social influence processes, remote off-grid communities*

Introduction

Residents of remote communities in Nigeria typically encounter challenges in actively participating in and benefitting from socioeconomic activities due to inadequate or poor access to electricity. Due to limited access to electricity, establishment, and growth of businesses in remote communities are hampered; in turn, restricting economic opportunities for entrepreneurship and local industries (Osunmuyiwa and Ahlborg, 2019; Adoghe *et al.*, 2023). This situation contributes to the economic marginalization of residents,

who also experience constrained opportunities for the social connectivity facilitated by digital communication. As a result, their ability to showcase produce and skills is limited. Inability to showcase produce and skills at a time when digital communication enables connections between buyers and sellers has consequences, such as wastage of farm produce, limited earnings, poverty and limited development (Pawlak and Kołodziejczak, 2020; Talema and Nigusie, 2023).

Despite supranational and national policy-backed efforts in Nigeria and other countries,

where energy deficit is high, slow progress has been observed in the adoption of technologies that could mitigate this deficit (United Nations, 2021). In response to this challenge, the United Nations is reversing its approach to energy transition in these countries, specifically, the body is expanding its scope of energy transition to include achieving SDG 7. In addition, the body is aligning the SDG goal with the goals of the Paris Agreement on Climate Change while simultaneously implementing the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. By this, the United Nations is adjusting its energy transition approach to encompass a more holistic strategy which focuses on achieving environmental sustainability, social inclusivity, and long-term development goals simultaneously (Pawlak and Kołodziejczak, 2020; Elavarasan *et al.*, 2021). This new approach emphasizes the need to update deployment policies which had previously focused mainly on cost and affordability of renewable technologies in pursuit of environmental sustainability.

Significant progress has been made in understanding how individuals' actions and decisions influence policy success (Mullainathan and Datta, 2014). Policy makers rely on two primary tools to shape individual behaviour: incentives and information. These tools are designed to encourage individuals to weigh the costs and benefits of their choices and act rationally. However, a growing body of empirical evidence suggests that individuals often deviate from rational behaviour. Further research, however, indicate that manipulating peer effects can induce faster adoptions of environmental-friendly technologies and practices (Verplanken *et al.*, 2008; White *et al.*, 2019).

Given the above, Saim and Khan (2021) call for policy decision makers to apply insight on social influence processes amongst peers in different contexts to develop effective solar home system deployment policies.

Lagos State, located in the southwestern part of Nigeria, is a major economic and financial hub, and the second most populous state in the country. Lagos State is known for its vibrant economy, bustling urban centres, widely diverse population and high energy demand. However, despite the economic prosperity of the state, a significant portion of the population, about 19%, live in remote, off-grid communities (Longe and Yaya, 2015) that lack access to reliable electricity. In recent years, the deployment of solar home systems has emerged as a viable and sustainable solution to address energy poverty in off-grid communities. The solar home system refers to a stand-alone system suitable for residential applications, such as home appliances, lighting, and computers. The solar home system is typically low capacity of about 100w, which is suitable for the electricity needs of households in remote communities (Salas, 2017). The system consists of photovoltaic modules connected to a PV charge controller, stand-alone inverter, and battery system that convert and utilize energy from the sun. The use of solar home system offers several advantages, including reduced reliance on traditional sources of energy such as kerosene or diesel generators; lower energy costs; and environmental benefits. Households in remote communities now have the option of installing the 60w pay-as-you-go option, which is offered by government-backed solar energy firms. The option enables households to make a modest initial investment and monthly incremental payments towards ownership of the technology. On the other hand, the comparable fixed cost solar kit installed by local technicians enables households make full initial investment on low-cost capacity as the 60w kit, and increase capacity gradually. Despite the availability of the technology, social influence processes impacting on solar home system adoption decisions within remote communities are largely unknown. Hence, the aim of this paper is to reveal the social

influence processes influencing adoption of the technology in three neighbouring communities on Tomaro Onisiwo Island in Lagos State.

The Study Area

The geographical extent of the study area stretches approximately between latitudes 6°420'N and 6°429'N, and longitudes 3°375E and 3°377'E. This area is about 227 acres of landmass located on Tomaro Onisiwo Island, an outskirt of Lagos State. The study area comprises three neighbouring communities, with distinct boundaries—Ilufemiloye, Akaponowa and Irede. Ilufemiloye has the largest landmass, with 189 acres and borders the Atlantic Ocean to the south. Akaponowa and Irede border the ocean to the north and cover 24 and 14 acres respectively. The study area is generally low-lying and flat, with elevations ranging between 0 and 20m (Fasona *et al.*, 2023). The vegetation is mainly mangrove and freshwater swamp forest (Adekanmbi *et al.*, 2023). The area

experiences the tropical wet and dry climate, similar to other coastal areas of Nigeria, characterized by distinct wet and dry seasons. Wet season is typically from May to October and dry season from November to April, with relatively high temperature throughout the year. Average solar radiation is about 12.6 MJ/m²/day (Ayodele and Ogunjuyigbe, 2015). The three communities are similar to others on the island. While Akaponowa is a fishing community, Irede is cosmopolitan, having inhabitants with varying livelihoods such as fishermen, civil servants, tailors, etc. Ilufemiloye is also cosmopolitan and mostly exclusive, inhabited by skilled technical persons such as marine engineers. Due to unavailability of census data for Tomaro Onisiwo Island, the aggregate population of the three communities was derived using the area-metric method (Lwin and Murayama, 2009). The aggregate population is estimated at 3,613.

Figure 1: Study Area in context of Apapa local government, Lagos State, and Nigeria

Materials and Methods

Data Collection

The study employed the interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) methodological framework. It was used to generate descriptions, and segment individuals’ experiences as regards their social interactions in relation to decision-making on solar home system adoption. To generate multi-perspective description of experiences of diverse individuals involved in solar home systems adoption decision, semi-structured interviews were conducted, with twelve participants organized into six (n=6) homogeneous subgroups. These are two (n=2) pay-as-you-go adopters, two (n=2) fixed cost solar home system adopters, two (n=2) non-adopters, two (n=2) local solar technicians, two (n=2) local solar marketers.

Participant Recruitment

In IPA, purposive sampling method is typically adopted to identify individuals who experience, or whose actions create a phenomenon (Kalu, 2019; Wright-St Clair, 2014). In this research, a combination of purposive and convenience sampling method was used to administer semi-structured interviews. In line with the multi-perspective approach in IPA, the researcher, with the help of a local informant, identified entities within the study area propagating solar home systems and household representatives with varying adoption decisions, who were accessible and willing to be interviewed. In total, twelve (n=12) individuals were identified. This small sample size is in line with IPA sampling approach. The IPA approach for sampling size

encourages researchers to determine a sample size that allows for the elicitation of in-depth insights and perspectives from each individual within the study (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2014). This approach emphasizes the quality of data over the quantity, aiming to capture the richness and depth of participants' experiences and meanings attributed to those experiences.

Material

Semi-structured interviews are specifically recommended for IPA. This is because IPA involves a cyclical process of data collection, analysis, and interpretation. Semi-structured interviews are well-suited for this iterative approach because they allow researchers to refine interview questions based on initial findings and emerging themes (Smith, 2004). Through the discussions in the semi-structured interview, participants provided in-depth explanation of their experiences on interactions relevant to solar home system adoption. Hence, questions were asked to guide, rather than dictate the course of the interviews. Participants were organized into six (n=6) homogenous groups depending on the peculiar propagating activity or adoption decision made. Then questions to guide discussions in each group were administered to the individuals within each group. Number of individuals and groups are as follows: two (n=2) pay-as-you-go adopters, two (n=2) fixed cost solar home system adopters, two (n=2) non-adopters, two (n=2) local solar technicians, two (n=2) local solar marketer. Questions to guide discussions with local solar entrepreneurs were focused on their marketing activities overtime. Questions included: Why did you decide to set up a solar home system business? How do you market solar home system option to prospects? How have their reactions influenced changes in your marketing activities? Questions to guide discussions with household representatives were focused on their reactions to local solar entrepreneurs' marketing activities and solar

home system adopters' feedback activities. Questions included: What were your considerations and actions after receiving the information from local solar entrepreneurs? Did you seek or receive additional information from previous adopters? Why did you choose this specific solar home systems options? The discussions with each participant were transcribed.

Data Analysis

The analysis was conducted in two stages, in line with IPA's idiographic approach (Larkin et al., 2019). First stage involved generating codes from transcripts, to represent and summarize the distinct experiences of each participant. Codes were developed based on interactions with other individuals in relation to solar home system adoption and follow up activities by self in relation to solar home system adoption. Superordinate and subordinate themes were generated from each participant's discussions on experiences interacting with other individuals and making solar home system adoption decision. The superordinate and subordinate themes of participants in each group were merged to develop superordinate and subordinate themes for each group. The second stage involved identifying patterns and their connections in superordinate themes from each group in line with the multi-perspective approach in IPA (Larkin et al., 2006).

Results and Discussions

The multi -perspective IPA approach resulted in the identification of three themes:

- i. Persuasion by local solar entrepreneurs: Appeals by local entrepreneurs to decision makers to consider the benefits of using solar home systems.
- ii. Word of mouth from previous solar adopters: Encouragement by solar home

- system adopters to non-adopters to consider the suitability of the technology.
- iii. Observational learning of solar home system usage: observing the usage of solar home system in comparison to the usage of

Persuasion by local solar entrepreneurs

Both decision-makers and local solar entrepreneurs noted that the provision of price-related information by local solar entrepreneurs, particularly comparing the

Extract 1

“They appreciated the advantages of solar home system over petrol powered generator in terms of absence of noise and smoke, but they were more

(Local solar technician)

Extract 2

“Engineer is my friend and I had been seeing him using solar. I liked the idea particularly because one does not need petrol to operate it. And when one thinks about petrol scarcity, technology is indeed a better alternative to petrol-powered generator. But I could not consider the technology because of the initial cost. However, when he calculated the amount of money I use in operating my generator and how much I could save installing solar home system in a year, I was convinced

Specific and relevant information provided by local solar entrepreneurs is influencing increasing adoption within the study area. However, persuasion which occurs when relevant information is received from sources considered credible (Klucharev *et al.*, 2008) is generally regarded as a task for policy makers, particularly where there is habitual usage of preexisting fossil fuel-powered alternatives (Lazdins *et al.*, 2021).

Word of mouth from previous solar adopter

Decision makers recall favorable mentions of solar home system in everyday conversations since the initial installation of the technology and this ultimately influenced their decision.

Extract 1

“I noticed my neighbor was using the pay-as-you-go solar. When we spoke, I asked him about how the technology works. He said he pays monthly. He told me how much it cost at the time, but when I decided to install mine, the price had increased a bit, but it was still

petrol-powered generator

Each theme is explored below.

costs of solar home systems to those of traditional petrol-powered generators, highlighted the economic advantages of solar solutions.

concerned about the financial implications for the community and know how petrol is accessed and regulated for use in households. When I started marketing with the chart, I got my first deal and others came afterwards”

and agreed to install the technology. I am now expanding my solar panels”.

(Fixed cost solar adopter)

Extract 3

“Marketer told me that the solar company is partnering with MTN and you can recharge every time with just 200naira per day, just like we recharge phones. I did not consider it for long before I agreed to installation”.

(Pay-as-you-go solar adopter)

okay”.

(Pay-as-you-go solar adopter)

Extract 2

“When I described my ordeal in accessing electricity through petrol generator during fuel scarcity last year, my sister highlighted the relief she has due to investing in fixed cost solar. I’m still considering between the pay-as-you go and the fixed cost solar”.

(Non-adopter 1)

Extract 3

“Yes, more and more people are using solar. I hear it is very good for electricity if one can afford it, particularly the ones the local engineers install. For example, at the charging station, the prices have increased from 50naira for phone alone to 100naira, so if along with the phone, you want to charge your fan, power bank and lamp, you would spend 200naira on each of those. In total then, one would be spending like 600 to 800naira at once for electricity access.”

(Non-adopter 2)

Evidently, favourable word of mouth ongoing in the study area is significantly influencing

adoption of solar home system, where preexisting alternative petrol-powered generator options remain. Based on several evidences, Kizilcec *et al.*, (2021) concluded that “word-of-mouth endorsements from friends, family members and neighbors allow households to understand the benefits and costs of solar home systems, and can

Extract 1

“When solar home system first appeared in the communities, it was a wonder. There was no noise and smoke which happen when using petrol-powered generator. We only saw light in the houses self-generating with solar home system. At first, it was the engineers who knew about it that were using it. After watching them for a while, I decided to adopt the solar too so as to reduce the stress of generating electricity with petrol-powered generator”.

(Pay-as-you-go adopter)

Household decision-makers tend to adopt the technology more readily when they observe its use and are satisfied with its functionality, leading them to make informed decisions (Saim and Khan, 2021).

Conclusion

This study indicates that interactions between entities in the local solar home system industry and household decision makers can be explored for increased adoption of the technology. Furthermore, it shows that current appreciation of the technology due to interactions between adopters and non-adopters can be instrumental to sustaining

significantly raise adoption rates, particularly in rural areas”.

Observational learning of solar home system usage

Decision makers highlighted the influence of observing the usage of solar home system on their adoption decision.

preference for the technology, particularly when economic conditions affect the choices of household decision makers.

Based on these insights, the study recommends the implementation of key strategies for developing solar energy for electricity in Nigeria, articulated in the country’s renewable energy and energy efficiency policy. Specifically, proposed micro-credit facilities should be made available to local entrepreneurs within the communities. Equally, the key strategy, training skilled manpower for the maintenance of installations should be expanded to include training on installation in partnership with established local solar technicians.

The social influence processes revealed in this research and the related activities of individuals, who engage in the processes provide policy makers insights into the distinct processes surrounding adoption of the technology in the study area. This knowledge positions policy makers to formulate strategic deployment policies for solar home systems in the study area.

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